

Plastic additive fate in soil, earthworms and barley: A 2-year field study

Aristeidis S. Tsagkaris¹, Darina Dvorakova¹, , Melanie Braun³, Virtudes Martínez Hernández⁴, Raffaella Meffe⁴, Vili Saartama⁵, Salla Selonen⁵, Sannakajsa Velmala², Jana Pulkrabova¹

¹Department of Food Analysis and Nutrition, Faculty of Food and Biochemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6 – Dejvice, Prague, Czech Republic

²Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke), Finland

³Institute of Crop Science and Resource Conservation (INRES) – Soil Science and Soil Ecology, Bonn University

⁴IMDEA Water Institute, Spain

⁵Finnish Environment Institute (Syke), Finland

The use of plastics in agriculture is necessary to obtain satisfactory crop yields and reduce the use of water and pesticides. During the synthesis of such polymers, the use of chemicals, known as plastic additives (PAs), is necessary to achieve the desired physical, mechanical and chemical properties. Nevertheless, most of PAs are not covalently bound on the polymer matrix, posing a risk of leaching into the environment. To monitor their fate, a 2-year field study was performed across Finland, Germany and Spain. At each site, 25 study plots were established for 5 treatments with 5 replicates: polyethylene (PE) and polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBAT) micronized pellets in concentrations of 0.005% and 0.05% w/w and controls. After the spiking of the soil, barley was grown in the fields. Soil, earthworm and barley samples were collected from the study plots over a two-year period to investigate the fate of 16 PAs. Using liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry, we quantified 5 different PAs in soils at concentrations reaching up to 278 ng g⁻¹ dw (irgafos 168). Earthworms living in soil containing 0.05% of PE particles were found to contain irganox 1010 in concentrations up to 135 ng g⁻¹ dw in all 3 countries. Importantly, no PA uptake was noticed for barley cultivated in the PE- and PBAT-contaminated soil. All in all, this is the first study comprehensively evaluating the fate of PAs in different matrices under real-life conditions.

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